

Possible Neuroinflammatory Mechanisms Which May Lead to Long-Term Neurological Disorders in COVID-19 Patients

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Abstract:

This review aims to provide insight into the possible long-term neurological complications that COVID-19 patients may develop after the resolution of intense acute inflammation characterized as “cytokine storm.” Neurological symptoms such as fatigue, headache, dizziness, nausea, confusion, dyspnea, anorexia, malaise, myalgia, ataxia, seizure, hypogeusia, and hyposmia are commonly seen in these patients. However, while lung inflammation dominates the acute stage of COVID-19 pathologies, some researchers believe neuroinflammation is more common than what is reported. Neurological abnormalities that are linked to neuroinflammation are of particular concern because neuroinflammation is hypothesized to cause neurological diseases such as Alzheimer’s disease, Parkinson’s disease, and schizophrenia. Many potential routes can lead to inflammation in the nervous system and elicit neuron cell death in COVID-19 patients. These include the potential neurotropic pathway of the novel coronavirus, CNS parenchymal infectability, thrombotic ischemic stroke, cytokine storm, and blood-brain barrier breakdown. Past pandemics of similar neurotropic viruses could also offer insights regarding the long-term neurological effects of COVID-19. In support of our speculation, the Spanish Flu pandemic of 1918-1919 saw an increased incidence of neurodegenerative disease, Parkinson’s disease, and schizophrenia. We do not know exactly what the future will hold for COVID-19; however, it is of paramount importance to attempt to anticipate and prepare for the possible chronic neurological sequelae and mitigate or prevent their effects.

Introduction:

The deadly pathogen responsible for the outbreak of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), emerged from Wuhan China in December of 2019. Within months of its emergence, the virus spread across the world infecting over 7,000,000 and killing over 400,000 people globally (1). Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) is seen in around 5% of COVID-19 patients and is associated with increased lung inflammation and upregulation of proinflammatory chemokines and cytokines (2, 3). Although ARDS is highly associated with COVID-19, there is a growing concern about the effects that COVID-19 may pose on the neurological system. Neurological symptoms are seen in 36.4% of non-severe and 45.5% of severe hospitalized patients (4, 5). The documented neurological manifestations of COVID-19 include fatigue, headache, dizziness, nausea, confusion, dyspnea, anorexia, malaise, myalgia, ataxia, seizure, hypogeusia, and hyposmia (4, 6). There is also a concern for stroke, encephalitis, and Guillain-Barre syndrome (7-9).

Though the high prevalence of neurological symptoms related to this disease is troubling, it is also important to attempt to anticipate what the future may hold when it comes to long-term neurological disease. The Spanish flu, caused by the H1N1 Influenza A virus, was known to also cause neurological symptoms and neuroinflammation. However, after the pandemic resolved,

there was an increased incidence of Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), and schizophrenia (10, 11). Will some COVID-19 patients experience the same fate? Only time will tell. Therefore, it is paramount to examine current neurological manifestations, possible neurotropic pathways, potential neuroinflammatory mechanisms, and causes of neuronal cell death of the disease to reveal possible long-term neurological effects.

1. Known Neurological Manifestations and Diseases Associated with COVID-19

1.1 Prevalence of Neurological Manifestations

Viruses, bacteria, and fungi are known to cause neurological problems. The neurologic effects of neurotropic viruses can range from transient headaches to permanent brain damage (12).

Research suggests that of hospitalized COVID-19 patients, about 24.8% experience central nervous system (CNS) symptoms, and about 8.9% experience peripheral nervous system (PNS) symptoms (5). Common CNS complaints include dizziness (16.8%), headaches (13.1%), and impaired consciousness (7.5%) (4). While common PNS complaints include hyposmia (5.1-20.4%) and dysgeusia (8.5%) (4). Most neurological symptoms become noticeable within the first or second day of the clinical symptomatic phase of COVID-19 (13).

Though most CNS and PNS symptoms seem fairly benign, there is evidence of more serious neurological disease. COVID-19 related ischemic strokes occur at a rate between 1.5% and 5.7% in hospitalized patients (7, 14). While the influenza virus has a stroke incidence of 0.2% (14). Other serious neurological issues that may manifest include encephalitis/meningitis and Guillain-Barre syndrome, though these are seen only sporadically (8, 9, 15).

1.2 Thrombotic Ischemic Stroke

The receptor angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) 2, can be found in lung, gastrointestinal, kidney, cardiac, and brain cells (16, 17). SARS-CoV-2 manages cellular entry by binding to the ACE2 receptor by its surface Spike protein (7). ACE2 is known to counteract the effects of ACE1 and angiotensin II. However, when SARS-CoV-2 utilizes ACE 2 for cellular entry, ACE2 may become depleted. High angiotensin II can lead to increased blood pressure, vasoconstriction, inflammatory, and coagulative effects(7). The result of this coagulative effect may lead to thromboembolism formation leading to cerebrovascular accident also known as a stroke. Strokes are typically seen two weeks after the onset of clinical symptoms (13).

In an observational study involving 186 critically ill ICU patients with COVID-19, Klok et al. found that 1.6% of the patients developed an ischemic stroke (18). Notably, COVID-19 related ischemic strokes seem to discriminately precipitate through the occlusion of the large vessels (19). Though the mean age of the patients involved in Klok et. al.'s study was 64 years old, ischemic stroke is not limited to the old. New emerging case studies show that stroke also occurs in young (< 50 years old) patients (20). However, it should be noted that many COVID-19 stroke patients have underlying health conditions such as hypertension and diabetes which are predisposing vascular risk factors (14). Stroke results in the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1, which can lead to increased neuroinflammation and further exacerbation

of brain injury (21). Thromboprophylactic treatment of critically ill COVID-19 patients is suggested (20).

1.3 Encephalitis and Meningitis

Currently, COVID-19 related meningitis/encephalitis remains an uncommon manifestation of the disease. Since the emergence of the disease, there have been only a handful of published case reports discussing meningitis and encephalitis in COVID-19 patients. However, given the prevalence of neurological symptoms, mild cases of encephalitis may go undiagnosed. Some researchers believe that encephalitis could be more common and may be one of the first manifestations of COVID-19(22). However, definitive diagnosis of COVID-19 related encephalitis is difficult because CSF titers of SARS-CoV-2 may be undetectably low, and viral dissemination may be transient (23). It is estimated that 20-50% of documented cases of encephalitis in the United States are due to viral infections (24). Encephalitis is known to be caused by HSV-1, HIV, Varicella-zoster virus (VZV), arboviruses, and enteroviruses.

The first reported case of SARS-CoV-2 related meningitis/encephalitis was announced in April of 2020. It involved a 24-year-old man who presented with impaired consciousness, neck stiffness, generalized seizures, headache, and nausea/vomiting. SARS-CoV-2 RNA was later found in his CSF by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) revealed atrophy of the right hippocampus and inflammation of the right hippocampus and mesial temporal lobe (15). COVID-19 related encephalitis seems to be self-limiting (23).

There is new evidence that suggests immune-mediated encephalitis of the brainstem may present post-infection. In a case report by Khoo et al., a 65-year-old patient experienced involuntary movements of her right upper limb 7 days after COVID-19 related symptoms resolved. COVID-19 infection was confirmed. Over a period of 48 hours, the involuntary movements progressed to her other three limbs and became unremitting. Cognitive ability also deteriorated over this time frame. She was given corticosteroids, and her neurological symptoms gradually improved (25).

2. Potential Neurotropic Pathway of SARS-CoV-2

2.1 Human-to-human transmission

Human-to-human transmission was established soon after the emergence of COVID-19. The United States confirmed its first case of COVID-19 on January 20, 2020 and five months later it had over 2,000,000 confirmed cases (1). Emerging information suggests that the average infected individual may have the ability to transmit the disease to as many as 3.28 others making SARS-CoV-2 more easily transmissible than influenza (26, 27). The primary route of transmission is via respiratory droplets spread from an infected individual to another. New information suggests that COVID-19 may have the ability to be transmitted by asymptomatic individuals (28). Once respiratory droplets are aerosolized, the virus can infect its new host through the lungs via inhalation but may also penetrate the body through the nose, mouth, and eyes (29).

2.2 Invasion and Dissemination

The lungs may hold the key when it comes to producing viremia and dissemination of the virus to the brain. As stated previously, once the virus is inhaled, it can obtain entry into lung endothelial cells through the ACE 2 receptor. Indeed, SARS-CoV-2 has been shown within lung endothelial cells by electron microscopy (30). A recent discovery by Ackermann et. al. showed a microangiopathic response in the lungs of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 at autopsy. The lungs displayed notable structural damage to capillary walls surrounding the alveoli in comparison to uninfected lungs (30). The capillary damage may be an additional route for which the virus may enter the bloodstream. Retrograde transmission from the olfactory tract to the brain has also been proposed as a method of SARS-CoV-2 transmission to the brain (31).

2.3 Penetration of the Blood-Brain Barrier

The Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) is a physiological barrier that separates the brain from the bloodstream. It functions to protect the brain from potentially harmful substances in the blood such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses (32). Many viruses are known to cross the BBB and precipitate neurological symptoms. These neurotropic viruses include Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Cytomegalovirus (CMV), Human Simplex Virus 1 (HSV-1), influenza virus, enterovirus, arbovirus, and more (33). SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV are also known neuroinvasive viruses, though the exact mechanism by which they penetrate the BBB is not well understood (34). There are three primary mechanisms that viruses utilize when crossing the BBB. The first approach, known as the "trojan horse," allows the virus to reach the brain parenchyma within an infected white blood cell (WBC) which then crosses the BBB paracellularly (between cells) (35). The second approach is when the virus crosses the BBB paracellularly without disruption of tight junctions (TJs) (35). The third approach is when a virus crosses the BBB transcellularly (through cells) (35). A possible route for SARS-CoV-2 BBB penetration is by the "trojan horse" approach as other coronaviruses have been shown to infect human monocytes/macrophages (34, 36).

2.4 CNS Parenchymal Infectability

After a virus enters the parenchyma of the brain, it may then infect the resident cells: neurons and glial cells. Many aspects of the neurological pathogenesis of COVID-19, including the ability to infiltrate neuronal cells, are not well understood. However, human neurons and glial cells express ACE 2 receptors on their cell membranes (16). This supports the neuroinvasive hypothesis of SARS-CoV-2 as ACE 2 receptors provide a target for viral entry and infection. SARS-CoV also expresses a similar spike protein on its surface, which recognizes ACE 2 receptors as a means for host cell infection (36). Further evidence shows that SARS-CoV can infect human neurons in-vitro and has also been found in cerebral neurons in autopsy samples (37, 38).

With a similar mechanism for cellular infiltration as SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 should potentially also have the ability to infect neuronal cells. A recent in-vitro study showed that SARS-CoV-2 does infect neuronal cells but less efficiently than SARS-CoV(39). Due to the novelty and pathogenicity of COVID-19, autopsy specimens showing that SARS-CoV-2 can

infect human neuronal cells are scarce. However, there is new autopsy information that provides significant insight into where the virus infects the human brain.

In a recent study, researchers at a teaching hospital in the United States performed autopsies on 18 diseased hospitalized COVID-19 patients in an aim to understand the effect the virus has on the brain (40). Brain samples were tested with quantitative RT-PCR for the nucleocapsid protein found on SARS-CoV-2. From the tested tissue, they found that 6 samples from 5 different patients were positive for the virus in the medulla oblongata and the frontal lobe. They also found acute hypoxic ischemic damage to neuronal cells in all 18 patients. This information shows that SARS-CoV-2 can infiltrate brain cells although the infection may be limited to small subdivisions of the brain.

3. Potential Neuroinflammatory Mechanisms Leading to Induced Neuronal Damage

3.1 Cytokine Storm Syndrome

Cytokine Storm Syndrome (CSS) can be characterized as a hyperinflammatory response that arises from excessive cytokine release due to unregulated immune system activation (41). This immunological overreaction can be a result of noninfectious or infectious disease such as COVID-19. CSS is of great concern in COVID-19 patients as it may be a leading cause of death (42). Cytokines associated with CSS include Interferons (INF), Interleukins (IL), chemokines, Colony-Stimulating factors, and Tumor necrosis factors (TNF), most notable of which are the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1, IL-6, and TNF-alpha (43).

Innate immune cells such as macrophages and dendritic cells contain Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs) which recognize Pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) located on various pathogens such as viruses (44). Once PAMPs are bound, these innate immune cells produce and release proinflammatory cytokines. These cytokines recruit other immune cells to the site of infection, which can result in endothelial cell damage, capillary damage, ARDS, multiorgan failure, and death (43, 45). High levels of cytokines can also pass directly from the lungs to the bloodstream achieving systemic circulation and dissemination in coronavirus infections (43). Once circulating in the blood, cytokines can reach the brain parenchyma through several methods. Research suggests that some cytokines can directly diffuse across the BBB and may also enter the brain through circumventricular organs, which are areas where the BBB is not absent or not complete (46).

Currently, literature data are lacking on the frequency that COVID-19 patients experience cytokine storm. Cytokine storm is difficult to diagnose, and septic shock or sepsis is often what is diagnosed instead of cytokine storm. However, IL-6, IL-10, and IFN-gamma are reliable markers as they are consistently high in the serum of patients with CSS (47). Patients with severe cases of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), caused by SARS-CoV infection, show high IL-6 and IFN-gamma levels; however, IL-10 levels are low (48). IFN-gamma, TNF-alpha, and IL-6 are at increased levels in COVID-19 patients (49, 50). IL-6 and the biomarker C-

reactive protein (CRP), show a statistically significant correlation with the severity of COVID-19 infection (50).

3.2 Breakdown of the Blood-Brain Barrier

CSS may result in ARDS as well as multiorgan system disease/failure (42, 51). Cytokine storm is known to affect the pulmonary, renal, hepatic, gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and neurological systems (41, 43, 52, 53). The BBB provides considerable protection to the CNS from pathogens and harmful substances. However, it is not impenetrable nor immune to physical damage. The BBB is composed of a capillary made of one endothelial cell welded to itself with tight junctions. The capillary is surrounded by pericytes, basal lamina, and astrocytes. The BBB can be damaged by the destruction of the basement membrane (BM) and TJs. Some viruses such as HIV can directly disrupt the TJs, however, there is a lack of literature on whether SARS-CoV-2 has similar capabilities (32). Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) cleave BM and TJ proteins and can be activated by ROS (32). SARS-CoV and other respiratory viruses have been shown to increase oxidative stress in the body(54). It is therefore hypothesized that SARS-CoV-2 may also increase systemic ROS leading to an increased breakdown of the BBB and vasogenic edema of the brain.

Another mechanism that may lead to brain inflammation through the disruption of the BBB involves ischemic stroke, which is seen in around 1.5% to 5.7% of hospitalized COVID-19 patients (7, 14, 32). Ischemic stroke can cause hypoxia and eventual neural tissue cell death. After hypoxic injury, activated microglia migrate to the affected area and release proinflammatory cytokines into the brain parenchyma (55). Cytokines from the brain and blood have been shown to help facilitate the BBB destruction and therefore increase brain edema (55). Hypoxia secondary to stroke may also directly lead to cellular swelling and lysis of the cellular components of the BBB diminishing its structural integrity. Late reperfusion of the brain can result in the injury of the BBB through oxidative stress destroying the TJs and BM by MMPs (32, 56). Disruption of the BBB may be another method for the passage of pro-inflammatory cytokines into the brain. In addition, research shows that some extracranial cytokines can damage the BBB thereby increasing its permeability (46).

3.3 Neuronal Cell Death

There are several potential avenues to explore when it comes to inducing neuronal cell death in COVID-19 patients. Cytokines/inflammation and hypoxia can lead to brain injury in COVID-19 patients. There is direct and indirect evidence that indicates that some cytokines are linked to neurodegeneration; however, some conclusions on the subject remain controversial. Some studies show that high levels of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1, IL-6, and TNF-alpha are associated with neuronal cell death (57, 58). In animal models, TNF-alpha and IL-1 exacerbate ischemic brain injury when administration coincides with the time of brain insult. Further evidence shows high endogenous TNF-alpha and IL-1 are seen after CNS insult and just before neuronal death in animal models. In humans, higher IL-6 and TNF-alpha are correlated with increased brain tissue injury and a worse clinical outcome after stroke or brain injury. TNF-alpha, in particular, can induce apoptosis directly through the induction of FAS receptors in the

CNS which initiates a cascade that results in apoptosis (57). Given that some COVID-19 patients experience cytokine storm, encephalitis, and stroke, they may be at higher risk for neuronal cell death (49, 50). In addition, the coronavirus HCoV-OC43 has been shown to induce apoptosis in neurons in-vitro (59). However, the literary evidence suggesting that SARS-CoV-2 can do the same is lacking.

Autopsy information does show that COVID-19 patients are at increased risk for brain injury and neuron death. In the previously discussed autopsy study by Solomon et al. involving 18 COVID-19 patients, researchers found that all 18 of the patients had acute hypoxic ischemic damage of neuronal cells in the cerebrum and cerebellum. Hypoxic brain injury may be due to a combination of not getting enough oxygen into the blood due to ARDS and/or the heart not pumping enough blood to the brain possibly due to a state of shock or cardiac arrest.

4. Potential Long-Term Neurological Impact of COVID-19

4.1 A Look at Historical Pandemics

The COVID-19 pandemic has been with us for less than one year. Though most COVID-19 related neurological symptoms are transient, it remains difficult to know exactly what the future will hold when it comes to possible long-term neurological disease. However, the key to understanding the potential long-term neurological side effects may lie with analyzing past pandemics and examining other neuroinflammatory viruses. The Spanish Flu pandemic of 1918-1919, caused by the H1N1 Influenza A virus, killed an estimated 40,000,000 and infected around 500,000,000 people globally (60). The Spanish flu, like COVID-19, had many neurological manifestations. Some of these include confusion, drowsiness, irritability, delirium, psychosis, and coma(10). The Spanish Flu has also been documented to precipitate many neuropathologies including encephalopathy, post-influenzal encephalitis, necrotizing encephalitis, chronic degenerative disease (e.g. Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Dementia), and Parkinson's disease (PD) (10). Other neurotropic viruses such as HSV-1, CMV, Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), VZV, and Hepatitis C virus (HCV) are associated with an increased risk of developing AD(61, 62). While Japanese encephalitis B virus, Coxsackie virus, St. Louis virus, HIV, West Nile virus, and Western equine encephalitis virus (WEEV) are all associated with increased risk of developing parkinsonism (63, 64).

4.2 Alzheimer's Disease and Dementia

AD is a common chronic state of progressive cognitive deterioration due to the degeneration of the brain. A patient with AD may show symptoms of retrograde amnesia, anterograde amnesia, confusion, aggression, personality changes, depression, and hallucinations. AD is associated with the accumulation of extracellular beta-amyloid plaques and intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles composed of tau protein. The accumulation of these insoluble toxic aggregates can result in synaptic disruption and neuron cell death (65). Though the exact neuropathogenic contributions of neuroinflammation are still not well understood when it comes to AD, there is emerging evidence that suggests neuroinflammation may initiate or exacerbate AD (66). This is of concern because COVID-19 is known to cause encephalitis and intracranial cytokine storm in some patients (9, 15, 67).

The AD pathogen hypothesis suggests that neurotrophic pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2, may cause AD by facilitating the aggregation and creation of beta-amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles through interactions with genetic factors and by causing neuroinflammation (68). Beta-amyloid occurs naturally in our brains and is destroyed by microglia. However, under excessive proinflammatory environments caused by infection, microglia are less efficient in their role of beta-amyloid clearance leading to accumulation (66). Beta-amyloid plaques themselves are pro-inflammatory, leading to a vicious self-perpetuating cycle of more inflammation and more beta-amyloid plaque deposition (66). Activated microglia also play a role in tau pathology as they can directly release phagocytized tau protein into neurons, which can lead to neuron cell death and cognitive decline (65, 69).

Apolipoprotein E (ApoE), is a protein that plays an important role in the development of AD. Patients who are homozygous for the ApoE e4 genotype, i.e. e4e4, show an increased risk for developing AD compared to patients who are homozygous for the ApoE e3 genotype, i.e. e3e3(70). In a retrospective cohort study involving 16,749 patients in the United Kingdom, researchers found that homozygous e4e4 patients are more likely to have a severe case of COVID-19 in comparison to those who are homozygous e3e3 (70). This may suggest a stronger link between AD and COVID-19 than previously thought as e4e4 genotypes may have an exacerbation of AD symptoms due to the novel coronavirus.

Though COVID-19 related AD is theoretically possible through the AD pathogen hypothesis, viral-induced AD remains a controversial subject. Chronic neuroinflammation is also critical when it comes to impairing mechanisms for abnormal protein clearance such as accumulations of beta-amyloid, which can lead to tauopathy (62). The prevalence of COVID-19 patients experiencing low-grade chronic brain inflammation is unknown. However, given the high prevalence of diffuse cortical neuron death seen in brain autopsy specimens, we may see an increase in non-AD related dementia in critically ill COVID-19 patients (40).

4.3 Parkinson's Disease

PD is a movement disorder caused by the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra within the midbrain of the brainstem and is characterized by tremors, rigidity, akinesia/bradykinesia, postural instability, and shuffling gait. PD is known to be caused by both genetic and environmental factors such as viral infections and neurotoxins like MPTP. PD, like AD, is an amyloidopathy and is associated with accumulations of amyloid fibrils of alpha-synuclein called Lewy bodies (LBs) (71). It is hypothesized that these LBs can lead to dopaminergic neural degeneration (72). Neurotropic viruses that cause encephalitis have been linked to both transient and permanent parkinsonism (64). However, the common viruses associated with parkinsonism, Japanese encephalitis B virus, Coxsackie virus, St. Louis virus, HIV, West Nile virus, and WEEV, have not been shown to induce LB formation (63, 64). Neuroinflammation then must be the primary link to dopaminergic neuronal degeneration in viral infection (73, 74).

Microglia and astrocyte-mediated neuroinflammation have been implicated in PD. IFN-gamma, which is seen at increased levels in COVID-19 patients, activates the pro-inflammatory state of

microglia which then releases pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF-alpha and IL-6 (45, 75). These cytokines then activate astrocytes, which in turn release ROS killing dopaminergic neurons leading to PD (75). COVID-19 related brainstem encephalitis has been reported (25).

The Spanish flu pandemic was known to cause encephalitis lethargica, lethargy induced by neuroinflammation, which could lead to postencephalitic parkinsonism (64). Children born during the Spanish flu pandemic were 2-3 times more likely to develop PD later in life than those not born during the pandemic (64). However, research on seasonal influenza suggests that it does not cause idiopathic PD but may contribute to transient PD-like symptoms (76). The discrepancy may be attributed to a decreased incidence of encephalitis in the seasonal flu in comparison to the Spanish flu. Indeed, microscopic examination of the brains of those infected showed new and old inflammation which may indicate a more persistent brain infection (77). Furthermore, additional neuropathologic examinations of the brainstems of patients with postencephalitic parkinsonism revealed neuronal loss in the substantia nigra (77).

4.4 Schizophrenia

Psychosis can be defined as a mental disorder in which one is detached from reality. According to the diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), schizophrenia is a long-term form of psychosis characterized by delusions, hallucinations, disorganized speech, disorganized behavior, flat affect, anhedonia, asociality, avolition and alogia for 6 months or longer. Psychosis can be linked to genetic and environmental factors and can be seen in about 0.7% of the population (78). The current understanding of schizophrenia shows that it may be induced after neurological insult, such as viral encephalitis and is more likely to precipitate in patients that have a genetic predisposition (79, 80).

It is theorized that increased intracranial cytokines, increased BBB permeability, and neuroinflammation can result in lasting neuropathological and psychological complications (46). The mild encephalitis (ME) hypothesis of schizophrenia states that low-level neuroinflammation, such as that caused by some viral infections, may cause an increased risk for the development of schizophrenia (80). Large comparative studies support the ME hypothesis showing that encephalitis caused by neurotropic viral infections, such as mumps, place patients at an increased risk for developing schizophrenia later in life (81). COVID-19 related encephalitis is believed to be more common than previously thought. This indicates that most of the COVID-19 related neuroinflammation may be low-level (22). New information suggests that between 0.9% and 4% of confirmed COVID-19 patients experience transient psychosis (82). However, whether this will lead to schizophrenia remains to be seen due to the novelty of COVID-19.

The Spanish flu was also associated with an increased risk of psychosis and the eventual development of schizophrenia. Evidence suggests that the risk of developing schizophrenia during the Spanish flu pandemic was increased for adults, children, and unborn babies (11). Schizophrenia risk was highest for the unborn babies of virally infected mothers (11). It is hypothesized that increased maternal and fetal cytokines may disrupt fetal neural cytokine networks responsible for brain development (83).

Conclusion:

Much is still unknown when it comes to the novel coronavirus. Neurological manifestations of the disease are widespread but remain relatively under-discussed. Common neurological symptoms include headaches, dizziness, confusion, hypogeusia, and hyposmia. While rarer and more serious CNS manifestations include stroke and encephalitis. The virus has the potential of neurotropism and may enter neuronal cells by utilizing ACE 2 receptors. Autopsy data and in-vitro studies are consistent with this hypothesis.

Past pandemics and other neurotropic viruses may help us anticipate the future when it comes to COVID-19 related neurological disorders. Neuroinflammation seems to be paramount in the precipitation of many of neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia, and dementia. Though COVID-19 related encephalitis occurs sporadically, some researchers believe it is more prevalent than we know. Potential mechanisms of neuroinflammation and neuron cell death are intracranial cytokine storm, BBB breakdown, and hypoxia. Autopsy brain specimens reveal that diffuse cerebral neuron death in critically ill COVID-19 patients is very common.

Given the evidence in favor of COVID-19 related long-term neurological disorders, we conclude that critically ill patients are potentially at greater risk for Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia, and dementia. We recommend prophylactic anti-inflammatory treatment in critically ill patients to minimize the possibility of protein aggregation and inflammation in the brain, which can cause neurological disease and deficits. These patients should also have regular follow-up visits with trained medical professionals to increase the probability of catching early signs of neurological disorders. Trained medical professionals should analyze biomarkers related to various neurological diseases. Catching early biomarkers can be critical for preventing, delaying, or stabilizing the progression of neurological disorders. We do not know exactly what the future holds for COVID-19 patients, but we must remain vigilant and proactively anticipate potential neurological sequelae to minimize long-term risks for these patients.

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